

COGNITIVE APPROACHES TO "PARABLE OF THE SOWER" BY "OCTAVIA BUTLER"

Yusupova Takhmina Mukhamatjonovna

Uzbekistan State World Languages University

takhmina_ym@gmail.com

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Abstract

This article applies cognitive poetics to the analysis of Parable of the Sower by Octavia Butler. Using concepts developed by Peter Stockwell, the study examines figure-ground relations, foregrounding through repetition, prototype theory, and embodiment. The analysis demonstrates how cognitive mechanisms structure readers' perception of dystopian space and highlight themes of survival, adaptation, and social collapse.

Key terms: cognitive poetics, Octavia Butler, dystopian literature, embodiment, prototype theory.

When reading a literary work, 'interpretations' of the text are often intuitive and formulated before analysis. Cognitive methods of interpretation seek to explain how this initial, intuitive 'interpretation' is formed into meaningful 'reading'. According to Peter Stockwell, cognitive poetics offers a model for linking the reader's subjective response with an analytical description of the text [Stockwell, 2002:8]. In this essay, we will apply cognitive approaches to the literary work Parable of the Sower by African-American writer Octavia Butler.

Parable of the Sower, written and published in 1993, reflects early 21st century anxieties. The dystopian novel imagines a near-future America, devastated by ecological problems and moral decay. The story follows Lauren Olamina, a young woman who lives in a community in California. After the tragedy which took all her family members and burned down her neighborhood, she decided to travel North. On her way, she met new people and they united as a community. Lauren founded a new belief system, called Earthseed, which centered on adaptation and change.

With regard to the cognitive analysis of the text, the first aspect to be examined is the distinction between figure and ground, which helps identify how certain narrative elements are foregrounded against broader social and environmental contexts in Parable of the Sower. In the fifth parable, Lauren writes, "It's raining... I can remember the rain six years ago, water swirling around the back porch, not high enough to come into the house, but high enough to attract my brothers who wanted to play in it" [Butler, 1993:76]. In this passage, rain acts as a figure, making Lauren's house the ground. If we compare this passage to a game of chess, the rain is the pieces on the board, which is Lauren's house. Thus, the author demonstrates the importance and value of rain for the people in the novel, revealing the problem of water scarcity. In the same parable, a couple of days later, Lauren wrote in her journal about the death of a little girl, Amy, again mentioning the rain: "I walked in the rain again this morning. It was cold, but good. Amy has already been cremated." [Butler, 1993:82]. Only this time, the rain is the ground, and Amy's death is a figure. The death of an innocent child is the key figure in this passage, pushing the rain into the background. This shift between figure and ground makes the text more dynamic, avoiding flat descriptions that lead to loss of attention during reading.

Moreover, Octavia Butler also uses lexical devices to create foregrounding. In particular, she employs repetition, mentioning the phrase "God is Change" over 17 times. This technique creates a sense of immersion and is a tool of manipulation. Lauren keeps a journal where she shares her thoughts and, in a sense, propagates her beliefs. By using repetition in Lauren's entries, Octavia Butler emphasizes the idea of Earthseed and impresses upon the reader its truth and importance, which can be considered as a psychological device [Stockwell, 2002:16].

An appeal to prototype theory allows us to consider "Parable of the Sower" as a text in which a dystopian space is constructed through blurred categories and the principle of family resemblance; the world is shaped through embodied experience; and reality is mapped onto basic-level categories [Stockwell, 2002:29]. Using prototype theory, we can see that categories are not limited to simple 'yes' or 'no', but rather have a center (the best examples) and a blurred edge (less typical cases). While "Parable of the Sower" can be classified as a dystopia, it cannot be the center. The prototype of a classic dystopia includes elements such as a totalitarian state, technological control, and a system of oppression. In the case of Butler's novel, there is no single totalitarian center, technological progress is not a key theme, and the novel is less about institutional threat than about everyday life. At the same time, numerous family resemblances are noticeable, such as violence, social collapse, and loss of security. Ultimately, we can come to the conclusion that "The Parable of the Sower" is not located in the center of the genre category, but closer to its blurred edge.

Octavia Butler skillfully uses language, accurately emphasizing certain details. Thus, through basic-level categories, she describes social collapse without resorting to abstraction, drawing on the theory of embodiment of conceptual patterns. The most powerful and obvious example of embodiment is Lauren's hyperempathy syndrome, which causes her to feel the pain and fear of others. Danger is recognized through the body faster than through conscious, which is why she is not always able to control it. The dystopian world is classified as "dangerous", "hostile", and "unstable" through bodily reactions. Octavia uses phrases such as "they eat bad food..." [Butler, 1993:14], "we went into the hills or bushes to sit down, drink water, eat dried food..." [Butler, 1993:277], "fires are illegal" [Butler, 1993:278], "the house was a ruin..." [Butler, 1993:241], and many other examples. In these passages, the highlighted words represent basic categories: home instead of safety, food and water instead of economic crisis, fire instead of disaster. All these words, as well as the words "wall", "road", "weapon", and "shelter", are associated with survival; they require no interpretation and directly relate to the characters' bodily experience. Through the prism of these words, Butler organizes the perception of the world at the level of everyday actions.

To conclude, cognitive analysis reveals how Octavia Butler structures readers' perception of Parable of the Sower. Through figure-ground shifts, repetition, prototype theory, and embodiment, the narrative emphasizes survival and adaptation in a collapsing society. These cognitive mechanisms help foreground key themes and shape the reader's understanding of the dystopian world.

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